

relation ($r = -0.628^{**}$ between minimum temperature and WL population (Table 1, figure). A significant negative relation ($r = -0.27^{*}$) existed between total rain-

fall and WL population.

The partial regression coefficient and the proportional contribution of the different weather factors on the light trap

WL population are in Table 2. Minimum temperature affected WL population most. □

Parasitization of gall midge by *Neanastatus grallarius* (Masi)

K. Potineni and R. K. Agarwal, Entomology Department, College of Agriculture, Raipur, M.P., India

Rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) was heavily parasitized by two chalcid parasites — *Neanastatus grallarius* (Masi) and *Platygaster oryzae* (Cameron) — in the GM-endemic area, College of Agriculture, Raipur, during 1981 kharif.

Parasitization ranged from 21 to 94% when 75 midges were observed each day in Oct and Nov. *N. grallarius* (Hymenoptera: Eupelmidae) parasitized GM pupae 1 mo earlier than *P. oryzae* and was pre-

Parasitism of chalcids on rice gall midge, Raipur, India.

sent through the third week of Nov, peaking at 75% parasitism (see figure). This is the first record of heavy parasitization of GM by *N. grallarius* in India. □

Complete slide sets of photos printed in *Field problems of tropical rice*, revised 1983, are available for purchase at \$50 (less developed country price) or \$60 (developed country price), including airmail postage and handling, from the Communication and Publications Department, Division R, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines. No orders for surface mail handling will be accepted.

Pest management and control NEMATODES

Nursery application of carbofuran for control of rice root nematode

E. I. Jonathan, agricultural officer; and B. Velayutham, nematologist, Nematology Laboratory, No. 16 E. V. R. Nagar, Tiruchi 5, India

Rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* causes substantial economic losses in lowland rice areas. The nematode damages the crop in the nursery and in the field. In 1981-82 samba we compared a nursery application of carbofuran 3% G broadcast at 1.275 kg ai/ha for control of rice root nematode with an untreated plot in a randomized block design with 16 replications in Panayapuram and Rachandarthirumalai villages of Tiruchi, Tamil Nadu.

Ponni and IR20 were planted in 3.75- × 2.5-m flooded plots at 15- × 10-cm spacing. Ponni was transplanted at 40 d and IR20 at 30 d. Carbofuran was applied 7 d before transplanting. Root samples were collected from the nursery by pull-

Rice root nematode population^a and grain yield after carbofuran application, Tiruchi, India.^b

Treatment	Nematode population/5-g root							Grain yield/plot (kg)
	Nursery		Days after transplanting			Before harvest		
	Before treatment	7 DAT ^c	15	30	60			
<i>Panayapuram</i>								
Carbofuran 3% G, 1.275 kg ai/ha	11.09	0.70	5.67	7.26	12.50	14.43	7.5	
Untreated control	11.23	13.91	14.30	16.44	14.82	15.00	6.9	
<i>Rachandarthirumalai</i>								
Carbofuran 3% G, 1.275 kg ai/ha	6.39	0.70	3.69	6.02	12.90	15.90	4.6	
Untreated control	6.18	7.14	8.51	13.53	14.98	16.43	4.4	
C. D. for population, 2.66		C. D. for yield, 0.196						

^aTransformed values. ^bMean for 16 replications. ^cDays after treatment.

ing 10 plants, at random, before pesticide application and at transplanting. Samples were taken from the field 15, 30, and 60 d after transplanting and just before harvest.

Nematode population was estimated by the Baermann pan technique using 5 g root/sample. The nematode population

data were analyzed after $\sqrt{x + 0.5}$ transformation. Grain yield was recorded. Results of the pooled analysis of infestation and yield are in the table.

Carbofuran application significantly reduced the rice root nematode population in the nursery and up to 30 d after transplanting. □